

THE INVESTIGATION ON INTERFACE OF CALL HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The interfacial properties and their effect on the shear strength of CALL laminates has been investigated. Expanding monomer was used to form CCVC as interfacial layer. It reduced the residual stress at the interface during curing and increases the interfacial shear strength up to ten percent. The shear strain of CALL beam has been investigated by TPB specimen. Moire fringes show that the shear strain in CFRP layer is much larger than the one in aluminum layers, but the envelope of them are nearly parabolic distributed along the cross section. Four point bending test of bimaterial beam composed of aluminum and epoxy resin was carried out to simulate the interfacial behavior of CALL. Pure shear strain exists on the interface and shear strain in the vicinity of interface has been obtained. The shear strain distribution is also obtained for specimen with interface crack.

INTRODUCTION

A series of research work on Aramid fiber reinforced AL Laminate (ARALL) were carried out in The Netheland. It was reported that ARALL possessed excellent fatigue properties, high tensile strength as composite and good impact resistance, machinability as metal.

Based on outstanding properties of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) carbon/epoxy aluminum laminate (CALL) was valued for its low specific gravity, low thermal expansion, high strength and long fatigue life^{[1],[2]}. Moire interferometry is a modern optical mechanical measurement method developed in 1980's. Since the advantages of high sensitivities, high quality of fringe pattern, in-situ measurement and whole field analysis, it has been widely used in the experimental study on new materials.

The research on interface properties of CALL is as following. First of all, the expanding monomer (NSOC) was used to form CCVC layer. It is expected considerable reduction of residual stress at the interface during curing, therefore the interfacial shear strength can be increased up to ten percent^{[3],[4]}. Then the shear strain distribution and failure mode of CALL beam with CCVC layer have been investigated. Finally four point bending test for bimaterials beam composed of aluminum and epoxy resin has been carried out to simulate the interfacial behavior of CALL specimen.

SPECIMEN AND EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

The unidirectional CALL specimen is composed of 13 layers of surface treated AL alloy sheet and 12 layers of carbon/epoxy layers prepared by hot pressing. Carbon/epoxy layer is composed of two preprag with thickness of 0.125 mm and AL sheet is 0.2 mm thick. For some of the specimen expanding monomer was used to form CCVC as interfacial layer. The longitudinal and transverse specimen with CCVC layer were cut from the fiber direction and perpendicular to fiber direction respectively (Fig.1). Bimaterial beam composed of epoxy resin and aluminum were prepared to simulate the interfacial behavior (Fig.2).

Fig.1 Specimen for Three Point Bending (unit mm)

Fig.2 Specimen for Four Point Bending (unit mm)

A high frequency crossed-line grating is replicated on the surface of the specimen and it deforms together with the specimen when loads are applied. The resulting fringe patterns is corresponding to those of Moire with 2400 line/mm. The experimental set up is shown in Fig.3. The in-plane U and V displacement fields (in the x and y directions respectively)

are determined from the fringe patterns with sensitivities of $0.417 \mu\text{m}$ per fringe order. The fringe patterns are contour maps of displacement governed by the relations

$$U = \frac{1}{f} N_x, \quad V = \frac{1}{f} N_y, \quad (1)$$

where N_x and N_y are the fringe orders at the point in the corresponding fringe patterns, f the frequency is 2400 lines/mm. A He-Ne laser source was used at a wavelength of $0.6328 \mu\text{m}$ and a power of 50 mw.^{[5],[6]}

Fig.3 Four-beam optical arrangement to produce N_x pattern with beam A and B and N_y pattern with beam C and D

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

THE EFFECT OF EXPANDING MONOMER ON THE PROPERTIES OF CALL

Certain amount of expanding monomer (NSOC) was mixed with epoxy to form CCVC (Copolymer of controllable Volume-Change on Curing) layer. The CCVC layer should considerably reduce the residual interfacial stress, therefore some properties of CALL can be improved. The interfacial shear strength has been obtained by using the short beam bending method. The results of shear strength of the specimen with CCVC layer is ten percent higher than the one of the specimen without CCVC layer. Another obvious indication is that the Moiré interferometry fringe patterns for these two kinds of specimen are quite different (Fig.4). The smooth fringe patterns of U and V field for specimen with CCVC layer means the strain field is continued across the interface. On the other hand the zig zag fringe patterns for specimen without CCVC layer shows the strain field is discontinued which caused by strong residual shear stress or local damage under bending. The results of in-plane tensile strength shown that there is little influence of CCVC layer on the tensile failure, since it is determined mainly by the fiber itself.

Fig.4 Moire interferometry fringe pattern for V field
 (a) with CCVC (b) without CCVC

THE SHEAR STRAIN DISTRIBUTION AND FAILURE MODE

Typical Moire interferometry fringe patterns are shown in Fig.5 (a), (b) for longitudinal and transverse specimen respectively. The in-plane shear strain can be deduced from fringe patterns of U and V field according to the following formula,

$$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{f} \left(\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial x} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $f=2400$ lines/ mm is the frequency of virtual reference grating; N_x and N_y are the fringe orders in the corresponding fringe patterns for U and V displacement field. The shear strain distribution curve across AA section are shown in Fig.6 (a),(b) for longitudinal and transverse specimen respectively. It is obvious from the shear strain distribution that the shear strain in CFRP layer is larger than the one in aluminum layer, but the envelope of them are nearly parabolic respectively, similar to an isotropic specimen. The reason to cause this is the difference of the shear modulus of CFRP and aluminum.^[7]

The main forms of bending failure for longitudinal specimen are delamination and the localization of shear damage caused by the matrix failure in CFRP layer. Specimen does not completely loss its load carrying capacity after delamination or shear damage appeared, which will expand further with the increase of load until the final failure.

Tensile failure of CFRP layer on the tensile side of the beam is the main form of the bending failure for transverse specimen. Tensile crack in 90 degree CFRP layer localized the damage. The damage also cause necking of the aluminum layer adjacent to the damaged CFRP layer, then leads to the final failure of the specimen. After the test a groove was found along the wideness direction of specimen on surface on the tensile side of the beam which is the result of necking in the aluminum layer.

Fig.5 U displacement field
(a) Longitudinal specimen ($P=200\text{kg}$) (b) Transverse specimen ($P=58.3\text{kg}$)

Fig.6 Shear strain distribution along cross section
(a) Longitudinal specimen (b) Transverse specimen

INTERFACIAL SHEAR OF BIMATERIAL BEAM

Four point bending test of bimaterial beam composed of aluminum and epoxy resin has been carried out to simulate the interfacial shear behavior of CALL specimen. The specimen and load set up are shown in Fig.2. According to the beam theory pure shear stress should exist on the interface. Moire interferometry has been used to obtain the displacement and strain field on the vicinity of the interface. Specimen with single and double interfacial crack have also been tested.

Typical N_x and N_y fringe patterns for a specimen with a crack at the bottom are shown in Fig.7. The total load is 712 N , corresponding to 89% of the failure load. It is obvious from the V field fringe patterns that the fringe on the epoxy side (left of the beam) is much denser than the aluminum side. This means that the displacement V of the epoxy part is much larger than the one of the aluminum part, it also shows from formula (2) that the shear strain of the epoxy part is higher than the aluminum part. This is because the shear modulus of epoxy is higher than the one of aluminum. The fringe pattern of U field shows that all the fringes across the interface are continued, which means the displacement u is also continued at the interface.

Fig.7 Fringe patterns N_x and N_y for specimen No.2 at load of 712 N
(a) U field (b) V field

The shear strain distribution along the interface shown in Fig.8 indicates that nearly uniform shear strain exists on the interface. The shear strain for specimen No.1 indicates that both the upper and lower interface cracks are separated, therefore the shear strain there are equal to zero. It is also shown that for specimen No.2 the bottom crack is not opened at all, so the shear strain there is not zero. A series of pictures which show the sequence of N_x fringe patterns at different loads are shown in Fig.9. The crack propagation and the crack opening displacement curve for the upper crack of specimen No.1 which are obtained from fringe patterns shown in Fig.9 are shown in Fig.10, which shows that the upper crack propagated from 0.84 to 1.33 mm and the COD from 3.5 to 12.5 μm .

Fig.8 Shear strain distribution along the interface ($P=712N$)

Fig.9 Sequence of N_x fringe patterns near upper boundary at different loads

Fig.10 Interface crack propagation curve and interface crack COD curve near upper boundary

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

The interfacial residual shear stress during curing can be reduced by using expanding monomer to form the CCVC layer between CFRP and aluminum layer. The interfacial shear strength is increased up to ten percent, but the in-plane tensile strength has little change.

The shear strain distribution along the cross section shows that the shear strain in the CFRP layer is much larger than the one in the aluminum layer, but the envelope of them are nearly parabolic similar to the isotropic beam. The shear failure at the interface or in the CFRP layer is the main failure forms for the longitudinal specimen and the tensile failure of the CFRP layer on the tensile side of beam is the failure mode for transverse specimen.

Four point bending test of bimetals beam composed of aluminum and epoxy resin was carried out to simulate the interfacial behavior of CALL. Shear strain distribution in the vicinity of the interface shows that nearly uniform shear strain exists on the interface. The shear strain on the epoxy side is much higher than the one on the aluminum side. The crack propagation and crack opening displacement are also obtained for a specimen with interfacial crack.

For further work, it is proposed four point bending test for a sandwich beam specimen with thin epoxy layer in the middle and two aluminum block on both sides. It should give improved result for simulating interfacial behavior of CALL.

ACKNOWLEDGE

Authors would like to thank for the financial support of the National Natural Foundation of China. The sincerely thanks to Prof. R. J. Wu, Prof. T. Y. Hu and Dr. K. Sun for their help and supports. Many thanks also to Ms. L. Z. Guo for preparing parts of the specimen for us.

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